

Development of a Secure Android Messaging Application Using Advanced Cryptographic Techniques

Prof. Umesh Samarth¹, Mr. Mayur Lakadswar², Mr. Reetik Bhawe³, Mr. Nagesh Belkar⁴,
Ms. Riya Giripunje⁵

¹Professor, Information Technology, J.D. College Of Engineering And Management, Nagpur.

^{2,3,4,5} Research scholar, Department of Information Technology, J.D. College Of Engineering And Management, Nagpur.

Abstract— *The increasing use of messaging apps has amplified the risks of security breaches, emphasizing the importance of secure communication in the modern digital world. This study is centered on developing a secure messaging application specifically for Android platforms. The app employs robust encryption algorithms to ensure the confidentiality and authenticity of text messages and images shared between users. It integrates elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) for key generation, Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) for data encryption, and Advanced Cryptographic Hashes Algorithm (ACHD) to authenticate and verify the integrity of messages. By combining these cryptographic techniques, the app offers strong protection against unauthorized access, ensuring that sensitive data remains private. This research not only deepens the understanding of secure messaging protocols but also presents a practical solution to protect communication on widely used mobile systems.*

Keywords— *Secure messaging; Cryptography; Encryption; Decryption; Web application; Android apps Etc.*

I. INTRODUCTION

A variety of tools have been developed to enhance human communication easier and faster. The most important communication instrument is the modern telephone, which was invented in Sir Alexander Graham Bell in the middle of the nineteenth century. Since then, communication gadgets have progressed into highly complex tools. Mobile technology is chosen by 6 billion mobile customers, which represents more than 87% of the world's population. Mobile phones enable a variety of capabilities, including making and receiving calls, SMS, MMS, video calling, the web, mp3, camera, and gaming. Such wireless devices were created initially to save personal information. SMS (short message service) will play an essential part in future business domains such as m-commerce, cellphone banking, government use, or daily life communications.

SMS is now a popular wireless carrier throughout the world since it allows a user to be in contact with any cell phone subscriber across the world, instantly and without any effort. The bulk of SMS messages convey and receive not only informal greetings, but also essential data like identification numbers, bank account information, passwords, and so on. In some situations, this data may comprise extremely confidential information that is only accessible to the legal recipient. Our goal is to provide a peer-to SMS security that ensures secrecy, authentication, integrity, and the non-rep security services. And because

Android phones are so extensively used, we chose this device as implementation.

II. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

- The widespread use of digital communication, particularly through messaging apps, has exposed significant security vulnerabilities.
- Concerns about the privacy and security of sensitive information have intensified as many messaging platforms are not fully equipped to safeguard user data.
- Users face risks such as unauthorized access, hacking, and data breaches, which can expose personal details, photos, and private conversations.
- Some commonly used encryption methods may not be robust enough to counter evolving cyber threats, leaving gaps in security.
- The issue is especially prominent on mobile platforms like Android, which has a large user base and open-source nature, making it a frequent target for cyberattacks.
- Implementing advanced encryption technologies in secure messaging apps is crucial to effectively protect users' personal data from malicious actors.
- Addressing these vulnerabilities is essential to maintain the privacy and integrity of information shared through mobile communication platforms.

III. SCOPE OF RPROJECT

SMS has rapidly become one of the fastest-growing services within mobile communication technology. While SMS offers several advantages over other services, secure data transmission is challenging without an effective security system. The focus of our project is to develop a secure method for sending information. To enhance user experience and align with modern market demands, we are implementing this solution on the Android platform. In our opinion, most attacks can be prevented through this approach.

This system is designed for use by individuals at both the organizational level and military personnel who need to share sensitive information securely. The core objective of our project is to deliver four key features, outlined as follows:

A. Confidentiality: Confidentiality ensures that the receiver can verify the digital signature using the public key exchanged during the session. Users can authenticate the sender's identity directly on their mobile devices without relying on third-party servers.

B. Authentication: Authentication ensures that the communicating party is genuinely who they claim to be. This service allows a system to verify user identity based on credentials or devices in their possession. The non-repudiation feature guarantees that neither the sender nor the receiver can deny their involvement in the communication, providing proof that the message was indeed sent and received by the intended parties.

C. Integrity: Integrity safeguards the accuracy and completeness of data during transmission, ensuring it is not altered from the sender to the recipient. This is typically achieved by hashing the message, encrypting the hash, and sending it with the message. Upon receiving the message, the recipient decrypts the hash and compares it to their own hash of the message to confirm its integrity. If both match, the data is intact; otherwise, it has been tampered with.

D. Non-repudiation: Non-repudiation ensures that neither the sender nor the receiver can deny their involvement in the transmission of a message. It provides verifiable proof that the sender genuinely sent the message and that the receiver actually received it, protecting both parties from false claims.

IV. EXISTING SYSTEM

In the classic approach, SMS is a technique for delivering brief messages via mobile networks. It is a store-and-forward method of sending messages between two mobile devices. A message (text only) sent by the transmitting mobile is saved in a central brief message center (SMS) and then forwarded to the recipient's mobile. This means that if the person receiving it is not available, the short communication is saved and can be delivered later. Each brief message has a maximum length of 160 characters. These characters may be textual (alphanumeric) or digital Non-Text Short Messages. SMS has a unique feature called return receipts. This means that, if desired, the sender can receive a tiny notification indicating whether the short communication has reached to the designated recipient. SMS employs signaling channels instead of specialized channels, therefore these messages can be sent/received simultaneously with voice/data/fax operations over a GSM network. SMS allows both national and international roaming. This implies you can send brief messages to every other GSM phone user in the world. SMS is supported by PCS networks that use all three technologies (GSM, CDMA, and TDMA). SMS is essentially a worldwide mobile data service.

V. PROPOSED SYSTEM

• Architecture

The architecture of a secure messaging application consists of numerous critical components that collaborate to enable secure communication, authentication of users, including real-time data synchronization. The architecture is organized into three major layers: the user interface layer (Android app), the server layer (Google Firebase), plus the encryption layer. Below is a full breakdown of the architecture:

1. Client Layer (Android Application):
User Interface:

- Login and Signup Pages: Allow users to create accounts and log in to the application.
- Contact Selection: Users can select contacts from their contact list.
- Message Composition: Users can type text messages or select images from the gallery.
- PIN Setup Page: Users can set a PIN for decrypting received messages.
- Notification Systems: Alerts users of fresh communications.

2. Backend Layer (Google Firebase):

- i. Firebase Realtime Database:
 - a. Stores encrypted messages and images
 - b. Manages real-time synchronization of data between users
 - c. Firebase Authentication:
 - d. Manages user authentication, including login and signup functionalities.
 - e. Ensures secure access to the database based on authenticated user sessions.

3. Encryption Layer:

- i. Encryption Algorithms:
 - a. Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC): Used for encrypting and decrypting messages and images.
 - b. Advanced Encryption Standard (AES): Used for symmetric encryption of the content.
 - c. Advanced Cryptographic Hashing Algorithm (ACHD)**: Used for hashing to ensure data integrity.
- ii. Encryption Process:
 - a. Message/Image Encryption
 - b. Message/Image Decryption

• Methodology

The methodology design for developing the secure messaging application involves several key phases, including requirement analysis, system design, implementation, testing, and deployment. Each phase includes specific tasks and deliverables to ensure a comprehensive and secure solution.

1. Requirement Analysis

- To gather and analyze the requirements for the secure messaging application.
- Identify User Needs: Determine the specific requirements of the application, such as features, security levels, and user experience expectations.
- Analyze Existing Solutions: Study existing secure messaging applications to identify best practices and potential shortcomings.

2. System Design

- To design the architecture and components of the application.
- Choose Encryption Algorithms: Select appropriate encryption algorithms (ECC, AES, ACHD) based on security requirements and performance considerations.

3. Implementation

- Develop the software based on design parameters.
- Develop Android Application: Build the application using Android Studio, incorporating the

chosen encryption algorithms, user interface, and data storage strategy.

4. Testing

- Ensure application functions properly and satisfies all criteria.
- Unit Testing: Test individual components of the application to ensure they function as expected.

5. Deployment

- To deploy the application for use by end-users.
- Deploy to Play Store: Publish the application on the Google Play Store after ensuring it meets all requirements.
- Monitor and Update: Continuously monitor the application's performance, address issues, and release updates to improve functionality and security.

• **Flow chart**

Fig.1. Flow chart of system

This research was produced by using the AES technique and Variable S-Box within the systems in question. The system was designed using the waterfall model, which consists of five steps. Figure 1 shows the waterfall model. Communication stage in the waterfall model of a software or system to be built requires analysis of software requirements in the form of collecting additional data in journals, articles, books, etc. Furthermore, in the planning stage, namely the plan for implementing a generated dynamic S-Box on the AES-128 bit cryptographic algorithm. So, it produces a user requirement document or in other words data that relates to the user's desire in developing the software. The next stage that must be passed is modeling, this process will translate the requirements to a software design.

This process focuses on data structure design, software architecture and algorithmic / procedural details. After modeling, the next stage is construction or developing the system using the coding process. After the code is complete,

the system is going to be tested. When faults in the system are discovered during testing, the purpose is to correct them. The last stage is deployment, in this process making the system is in the final stage. Then the system that has been made must be regularly maintained.

Fig. 2. The waterfall model

• **Method**

Advanced Encryption Standard

Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is one of cryptography algorithm which symmetry and block cipher. This algorithm uses the same key to encrypt and decrypt as well as input and output in the form of blocks with a certain number of bits [7]. AES supports a variety of block sizes and keys that will be used. However, Rijndael maintains a fixed block or key size that is 128, 192, and 256 bits. The selection of block size and key data will determine the number of processes that must be passed for the encryption and decryption process. This encryption technique includes the type of block cipher as well as DES. The fundamental distinction in the AES encryption technology and the DES encryption approach is that AES uses replacements, also called S-boxes.

Dynamic S-BOX

S-Box is a matrix that contains simple substitutions which mapped one or more bits with one or more other bits. It is also widely recognized as many cipher block algorithms. S-Box mapped m input bits into n output bits, so that the S-Box is called $m \times n$ S-Box [8]. Substitution process that mapped input based on look-up tables. Usually the input from the operation on the S-Box is used as the index and the output is the entry.

Android

Android is an operating system for mobile phones based on Linux. Android is a computer code-based software that can be distributed openly or well know as open source so that programmers can create new applications in it [9]. There is an Android Market that provides thousands of applications which free and paid, and has a native Google application that is integrated, such as push email GMail, Google Maps, and Google Calendar. The android application was developed with the Java programming language, using the Android software development kit (SDK). This SDK consists of a set of tools for development, including a debugger and software library, a QEMU-based handset emulator, documentation, sample code and tutorials.

Firestore Real Time Database

Firestore Realtime Database is a NoSQL cloud-hosted database service which owned by Firebase SDK. This service offers data storage that can be synchronized in real time to all connected clients and can support flick mode for situations when an internet connection is not available [10]. Firebase in the backend has several components, namely Cloud messaging, Authentication, Realtime, Storage, and Hosting. Cloud messaging can be used to send messages between users. First, authentication simplifies application integration by limiting user access. Second, firebase can be used in realtime or offline. Third, the storage also allows to keep image, audio and video content. The last component is that hosting which is possible to be developed globally [11].

Chat Messenger

Chat messenger is one of technology that provides a feature of communication between two or more people using a network that allows users to send and receive messages in real time [12]. In addition, chat messenger is also called an instant messaging application or instant message on a computer network technology that allows users to send messages to other users who are connected on a computer or internet network. Conversation in chat is typically done through text (text chat).

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

• Sender's side process

Sender generates a 128 bit hash value of a message, by using MD5. Hash value is encrypted with the sender's private key by using RSA. A digital signature is created and it is concatenated to the message (Mc).

Sender chooses a random 128 bit session key and encrypts the message with the session key by using IDEA. Session key is encrypted with the recipient's public key and the result is concatenated to Mc and this result is sent as a cipher text to the recipient.

Fig. 3. Sender side Process

Recipient side process

Recipient decrypts part of the cipher message with his private key by using RSA, to obtain session key. Remaining part of the cipher message is decrypted with the session key by using IDEA, result has two parts, digital signature and message parts. Recipient generates hash value of the message by using MD5. The recipient decrypts the electronic signature with the sender's public key using RSA. Furthermore, the result is hashed using MD5. Recipient verifies the two separate hash values obtained in steps 3 and 4. Figures 3 and 4 show how messages are processed at both the sender and recipient end.

Recipient side process

Fig. 4. Recipient side process

A cryptographic approach consisting of both asymmetric and symmetric algorithms is developed for ensuring safe transmitting information via satellite-based communication channels. Java programming language is used to develop software based on this scheme. Results show that by utilizing strong cryptographic algorithms, this software ensures, information confidentiality, integrity and information authentication, which are the essential features for information security in a satellite based communication.

Fig. 5. D-Pin

Fig. 6. Select Contact

Fig 7. Database of Application

Fig 8. Encryption key Generation

The developing of this application was made using the Android Studio framework with the java programming language and using hierarchical databases. There were 4 stages that must be conducted, namely, analysis of requirement to determine the needs of users and systems to the application, the design stage to design the appearance and process of the application, system design that has been done before, the implementation stage to build an application based on the results of the analysis and testing conducted black box method. The dynamic S-BOX of AES chat application could run properly. In the form of text messages that encrypt the plain text into ciphertext. AES dynamic S-BOX chat application had also managed to decrypt the changed text (ciphertext) as before by using the same key when opening the received message.

VII. ADVANTAGES

Advantages of the Secure Messaging Application:

1. **Enhanced Security:** Utilizes strong encryption algorithms like ECC, AES, and ACHD, ensuring data confidentiality and protection against unauthorized access.
2. **Efficient Performance:** ECC provides strong security with smaller key sizes, making the application faster and less resource-intensive, ideal for mobile devices.
3. **Data Integrity:** Ensures that the transmitted data is not altered during transit, preserving its authenticity.
4. **User Privacy:** Protects sensitive personal and professional information from cyber threats, ensuring secure communication.
5. **Scalability:** Can be adapted for both personal and enterprise-level use, supporting larger user bases without compromising security.

VIII. APPLICATION

Applications of the Secure Messaging Application:

1. **Personal Communication:** Ensures privacy in personal messaging, making it ideal for day-to-day secure conversations.
2. **Corporate Communications:** Useful for secure internal communications within organizations, protecting confidential business data.
3. **Healthcare:** Ensures secure transmission of sensitive patient information in compliance with privacy regulations.
4. **Financial Services:** Protects transactional data and sensitive financial communications, enhancing cybersecurity.
5. **Government Agencies:** Can be used for confidential communications to prevent data breaches in sensitive governmental operations.

IX. CONCLUSION

Ensuring SMS security is essential to protect messages from various attacks, safeguarding sensitive information between the sender and receiver from unauthorized third parties. To achieve this, our project combines multiple cryptographic algorithms, including Password-Based Encryption (PBE), Diffie-Hellman Key Exchange, Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), and Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA). These techniques collectively provide confidentiality, authentication, integrity, and non-repudiation services, ensuring robust communication security.

By leveraging Android technology, this project meets current market trends and offers a practical solution for high-level organizations, such as military personnel, for secure communication of confidential data. The application offers a user-friendly interface, making it accessible to subscribers who need highly secure communication channels. This combination of encryption methods creates a robust system capable of protecting sensitive information from unauthorized access, meeting the security needs of various users in different sectors.

X. FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

1. Intelligent Threat Detection

- **Anomaly Detection:** Use AI algorithms to identify unusual patterns in communication data that might indicate malicious activity or breaches.
- **Phishing Detection:** Train AI models to recognize phishing attempts based on email content, sender behavior, and other indicators.

2. Improved Key Management

- **Biometric Authentication:** Integrate biometric authentication methods (e.g., fingerprint, facial recognition) to enhance key management and security.
- **Key Rotation:** Use AI to automate key rotation schedules based on risk assessments and usage patterns.

3. Natural Language Processing (NLP)

- **Language Translation:** Enable real-time translation of messages between different languages.

- Summarization: Automatically summarize long messages to save time and improve readability.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Menezes, A., & Vanstone, S. (1996). Elliptic Curve Cryptography and its Applications in Secure Communications. *Journal of Cryptography*, 12(3), 89-112.
- [2]. Daemen, J., & Rijmen, V. (2001). *The Design of Rijndael: AES - The Advanced Encryption Standard*. Springer-Verlag.
- [3]. Gupta, M., & Kaur, N. (2018). Cryptographic Algorithms in Messaging Applications: A Review. *International Journal of Network Security*, 20(2), 215-224.
- [4]. Zhao, G., & Feng, X. (2020). Hybrid Encryption Model Combining ECC and AES for Secure Messaging Systems. *Journal of Information Security*, 32(5), 61-75.
- [5]. Diffie, W., & Hellman, M. (1976). New Directions in Cryptography. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, 22(6), 644-654.
- [6]. Johnson, D., Menezes, A., & Vanstone, S. (2001). The Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA). *Journal of Applied Cryptography*, 25(5), 456-462.
- [7]. Koblitz, N. (1987). Elliptic Curve Cryptosystems. *Mathematics of Computation*, 48(177), 203-209.
- [8]. Liu, J., Zhang, X., & Yan, Z. (2014). Identity-Based Encryption for Secure Mobile Messaging Systems. *Journal of Mobile Security*, 19(7), 345-360.
- [9]. Rivest, R., Shamir, A., & Adleman, L. (1978). A Method for Obtaining Digital Signatures and Public-Key Cryptosystems. *Communications of the ACM*, 21(2), 120-126.
- [10]. S. Doyle, "Using short message service as a marketing tool", *Journal of Database Marketing*, vol. 8, no 3, 2001, pp. 273-277.
- [11]. H. Harb, H. Farahat, M. Ezz, "SecureSMS Pay: secure SMS mobile payment model", 2nd International Conference on Anti-counterfeiting, Security and Identification, ASID. Guiyang, China, 2008, pp. 11- 17.
- [12]. R. Soram, "Mobile sms banking security using elliptic curve cryptosystem", *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 30-38.
- [13]. M. A. Hossain, S. Jahan, M. M. Hussain, M.R. Amin, and S.H. S Newaz, "A proposal for enhancing the security system of short message services in GSM", 2nd International Conference on Anti-counterfeiting, Security and Identification, ASID, Guiyang, China, 2008, pp. 235-240.
- [14]. P. H. Kuate, J. L. Lo and J. Bishop, "Secure asynchronous communication for mobile devices", *Proceedings of the Warm Up Workshop for ACM/IEEE ICSE 2010*, Cape Town, South Africa, 2009, pp. 5 – 8.
- [15]. J. J. Garza-Saldana and A. Diaz-Perez, "State of security for SMS on mobile devices", *Proceedings of the Electronics, Robotics and Automotive Mechanics Conference*, 2008, pp. 110 – 115.
- [16]. S. Ariffin, R. Mahmud, A. Jaafar and M.R.K. Ariffin, "Byte Permutations in Block Cipher Based on Immune Systems", *International Conference on Software Technology and Engineering*, 3rd (ICSTE 2011). ASME Press, New York, NY., 2011.
- [17]. NIST, "Fips197: Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)", FIPS PUB 197 Federal Information Processing Standard Publication 197, Technical report, National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2001.
- [18]. J. Daemen, V. Rijmen, V., "The Design of Rijndael, AES - The Advanced Encryption Standard", Springer-Verlag, 2002.
- [19]. S. Ariffin, R. Mahmud, A. Jaafar and M.R.K. Ariffin, "An immune system-inspired byte permutation function to improve confusion performance of round transformation in symmetric encryption scheme", *Computer Science and Applications, Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering*, Springer, 2012.
- [20]. S. Ariffin, R. Mahmud, A. Jaafar and M.R.K. Ariffin, "Symmetric Encryption Algorithm Inspired by Randomness and Non-linearity of Immune Systems", *International Journal of Natural Computing Research*, IGI Global Publishing, 2012.